

Tensile Behavior and Stress Relaxation of Uncured Prepreg of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Materials

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UNIVERSITY OF DELAWARE
**CENTER FOR
COMPOSITE MATERIALS**
Celebrating 50 Years

“Tensile Behavior and Stress Relaxation of Uncured Prepreg of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Materials”

Objectives

- Characterize tensile behavior of uncured TuFF under uniaxial loading.
- Develop and validate a continuum constitutive model.
- Enable forming process simulations for TuFF prepreg.
- Approach
 - Perform room temperature tensile tests over wide range of strain rates.
 - Analyze recorded video for strain measurement.
 - Formulate and validate constitutive expressions.
 - Implement model in commercial forming software.
 - Validate forming simulations with experimental results.

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- Forming of Fiber-Reinforced Composites
 - Continuous fibers offer strength, but poor formability.
 - Aligned Discontinuous Fiber (ADF) composites (like TuFF) balance formability and performance.
- TuFF Forming Opportunities and Challenges
 - **Significant** fiber-direction stretchability (e.g. local maximum strain 42%)
 - **Lack of constitutive models** capturing anisotropic mechanical behavior of uncured prepreg.

- Methodology:
 - I. **Design** experimental framework for tensile testing of uncured TuFF prepreg.
 - II. **Characterize** strain-rate dependent viscous response in fiber direction.
 - III. **Develop** continuum constitutive model using normalized master curve.
 - IV. **Implement** model in composite forming simulation software.

Experimental Procedure

• Materials and Conditions

- Prepreg: 3mm IM7 carbon fiber with Axiom (Ax-2201FR) thermoset resin.
- Volume fraction: 40%
- Areal Weight: 120gsm
- Specimens: 4" gauge length x 1" width x 0.25mm Thickness.
- Room temperature conditioning.

• Sample Preparation

- Utilized mirror-finished aluminum fixture for end-tab bonding.
- Applied a dot-grid pattern on specimens surface using an acrylic stencil.

• Experimental Setup

- Captured force and cross-head displacement via Instron (2kN load cell - 1000Hz)
- Recorded deformation by HD digital video camera (24 fps)

- Preliminary Data

- Uniaxial tensile test at **constant strain rates** (x3/x5 replicates per strain rate).
- Strain rates (displacement velocity) spanning three orders of magnitude (displacement velocities: 0.02 to 20 *in/min*).

Displacement Rate (inch/min)	Strain Rate (1/s)	Yield Stress (MPa)		Yield Strain (%)	
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
0.02	8.33e-05	4.16	0.19	0.23	0.025
0.2	8.33e-04	21.60	0.92	0.61	0.007
2.1	8.75e-03	118.36	5.41	1.33	0.031
20	8.33e-02	296.29	12.23	2.05	0.134

- **Reliable Experimental Data**
 1. High experimental repeatability (< 5%).
 2. Low material variability.
- **Similar Normalized Response.**

- Approach
 1. Convert *Force-Displacement* to *Eng. Stress-Strain*.
 2. Split material response in two distinct regions:
 - a) Pre-Yield (Region I)
 - b) Post-Yield (Region II)
 3. Propose Individual rate-dependent models for **Pre-Yield** and **Post-Yield** regions with smooth transition at yield.

Constitutive Model Formulation – Constant Strain Rate Loading

- Yield Stress (σ_0) increase with increasing Strain Rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$)
- Implemented Model (Eyring Yielding model):

$$\sigma_{0(\dot{\epsilon})} = A \cdot \ln\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{C_1}\right) + B \cdot \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{C_2}\right) + D$$

- Assumptions:

- Plateau at very low strain rates (half the yield stress). $D = \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_{min}}{2}$
- Keep yield stress positive at very low strain rates. $C_1 = \dot{\epsilon}_{min}$

- Similar procedure for Yield Strain (ϵ_0)

Yield Stress	Yield Strain
$\sigma_{0(\dot{\epsilon})} = A \ln\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{C_1}\right) + B \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{C_2}\right) + D$	$\epsilon_{0(\dot{\epsilon})} = a \ln\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{c_1}\right) + b \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{c_2}\right) + d$
$A = 8.50 e - 03$	$a = 6.65 e - 06$
$B = 5.93 e + 01$	$b = 2.92 e - 03$
$C_1 = 8.33 e - 05$	$c_1 = 8.33 e - 05$
$C_2 = 2.50 e - 03$	$c_2 = 2.97 e - 04$
$D = 2.08$	$d = 1.20 e - 03$

Constitutive Model Formulation – Constant Strain Rate Loading

- Pre-Yield (Region I) Modeling: Non-linear Hardening

- Normalized Stress ($\bar{\sigma}$) – Normalized Strain ($\bar{\epsilon}$) (with respect to *Yield Stress* and *Yield Strain*).

- Implemented Model :

$$\bar{\sigma}(\bar{\epsilon}, \dot{\epsilon}) = \frac{\bar{E}_{(\dot{\epsilon})} \cdot \bar{\epsilon}}{\left(1 + (\bar{E}_{(\dot{\epsilon})} \cdot \bar{\epsilon})^{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\epsilon})}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\epsilon})}}}}$$

- Fitting Parameters:

- $\bar{E}_{(\dot{\epsilon})}$: Initial Slope (Initial Normalized Stiffness)
- $\bar{n}_{(\dot{\epsilon})}$: Asymptotic Plateau shape

- Pre-Yield (Region I) Model Validation

- Denormalizing the model prediction (normalized stress - strain) by multiplying them to yield stress and yield strain.

$$\sigma(\bar{\epsilon}, \dot{\epsilon}) = \sigma_0(\dot{\epsilon}) \cdot \frac{\bar{E}(\dot{\epsilon}) \cdot \bar{\epsilon}}{\left(1 + (\bar{E}(\dot{\epsilon}) \cdot \bar{\epsilon})^{\bar{n}(\dot{\epsilon})}\right)^{\frac{1}{\bar{n}(\dot{\epsilon})}}}$$

- High Strain Rate Data

- Low Strain Rate Data

Constitutive Model Formulation – Constant Strain Rate Loading

- Post-Yield (Region II) Modeling: Exponential Softening

- Normalized Stress ($\bar{\sigma}$) – Relative Strain ($\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0$)

- Implemented Model :

$$\bar{\sigma}(\varepsilon, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{array}{c} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^*(\dot{\varepsilon})} \right)^{m(\dot{\varepsilon})} \right] \\ + \\ \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^{**}(\dot{\varepsilon})} \right)^{M(\dot{\varepsilon})} \right] \end{array} \right)$$

- Fitting Parameters:

- $\varepsilon^*(\dot{\varepsilon}) / \varepsilon^{**}(\dot{\varepsilon})$: Decay Coefficient
 - $m(\dot{\varepsilon}) / M(\dot{\varepsilon})$: Softening Strain Scales

- Post-Yield (Region II) Model Validation

1. Stress decays exponentially toward zero in the post-yield regime (desirable for implementation in forming simulations).
2. Prediction error is comparable to variation across replicates.
3. Stress can get de-normalized with respect to yield stress.

- Characterized Models

- Yield Stress (σ_0) and Strain (ε_0)

$$\sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})} = A. \ln\left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{c_1}\right) + B. \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{c_2}\right) + D$$

$$\varepsilon_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})} = a. \ln\left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{c_1}\right) + b. \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{c_2}\right) + d$$

- Pre-Yield Non-linear Hardening

$$\sigma(\varepsilon, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \frac{\bar{E}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \bar{\varepsilon}}{\left(1 + (\bar{E}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \bar{\varepsilon})^{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}}}$$

$$\bar{E}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} = E_a \log(\dot{\varepsilon}) + E_b \quad \bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})}}$$

$$\bar{n}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} = n_a \log(\dot{\varepsilon}) + n_b$$

- Post-Yield Softening

$$\sigma(\varepsilon, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})}}{2} \left(\exp\left[-\left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^*_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}\right)^{m_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}\right] + \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^{**}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}\right)^{M_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}\right] \right)$$

$$\varepsilon^*_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} = a^* \exp(b^* \dot{\varepsilon}) + c^*$$

$$\varepsilon^{**}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} = a^{**} \exp(b^{**} \dot{\varepsilon}) + c^{**}$$

$$M_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} = P \dot{\varepsilon} + Q$$

$$m_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} = p \dot{\varepsilon} + q$$

- Material response validation across 3 orders of strain rate magnitude (22 fitting parameters).

- High Strain Rate Data

- Low Strain Rate Data

- Strain Rate Dependent Constitutive Tensile Behavior (Family of curves)

- Predicted curves covering strain rates from very low to very high levels
- Lower Strain Rates:
 - Lower yield stress,
 - Earlier yielding at smaller strains,
 - Gradual softening.
- Higher Strain Rate:
 - Higher yield stress,
 - Larger strain before yielding,
 - Sharp stress decay after yield.
- Tabular inputs for ABAQUS explicit solver

Constitutive Model Formulation – Stress Relaxation

• Experimental Procedure and Data

- **Loading at constant strain rate, followed by stress relaxation hold at defined strain levels.**

- **Strain levels :** $\left[\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{4}, 1, \frac{5}{4}, \frac{6}{4} \right] * \epsilon_0$

- Each test includes 6 sequential loading –relaxation cycles.

- The first Loading-Relaxation cycle results.

- Stress decay curves isolated for relaxation model fitting.

Constitutive Model Formulation – Stress Relaxation

- Stress Decay Model
 - Fully viscous response.
 - Dependency on the strain rate of the prior loading interval.
 - No significant strain dependency.

- Implemented Model :

$$\bar{\sigma}(t, \dot{\epsilon}) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t}{\tau(\dot{\epsilon})} \right)^{n(\dot{\epsilon})} \right]$$

- Parameters:

- $\tau(\dot{\epsilon})$: Characteristic Time
- $n(\dot{\epsilon})$: Exponent Parameter

- Stress Relaxation Time scales: 1-10 seconds

Constitutive Model Formulation – Stress Relaxation

Stress Relaxation Model Validation

- Constant strain rate ($8.75 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
- Up to 0.64% strain.
- 30s of stress decay

- Constant strain rate ($8.75 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
- Up to 2.6% strain.
- 30s of stress decay

Constitutive Model Formulation – Incremental Formulation

- Incremental Formulation for Software Implementation

$$\sigma^{new} = \sigma^{old} + \Delta\sigma$$

- Stress increment formulations:

$$\Delta\sigma = \frac{\partial\sigma}{\partial\varepsilon} \Delta\varepsilon + \frac{\partial\sigma}{\partial\dot{\varepsilon}} \Delta\dot{\varepsilon}$$

- Chain rule differentiation

Pre-Yield

$$\sigma(\varepsilon, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \frac{\bar{E}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \bar{\varepsilon}}{\left(1 + (\bar{E}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \bar{\varepsilon})^{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}}}$$

Post-Yield

$$\sigma(\varepsilon, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})}}{2} \left(\exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^*_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right)^{m_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right] + \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^{**}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right)^{M_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right] \right)$$

Stress Relaxation

$$\sigma(t, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t}{\tau_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right)^{n_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right]$$

- Constitutive Model in Fiber Direction

- Pre-Yield

$$\sigma(\varepsilon, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \frac{\bar{E}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \bar{\varepsilon}}{\left(1 + (\bar{E}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})} \cdot \bar{\varepsilon})^{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\bar{n}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}}}}$$

- Post-Yield

$$\sigma(\varepsilon, \dot{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\sigma_{0(\dot{\varepsilon})}}{2} \left(\exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^*_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right)^{m_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right] + \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon^{**}_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right)^{M_{(\dot{\varepsilon})}} \right] \right)$$

Explicit Implementation
 (Tabular inputs by family curves)

Implicit Implementation
 (Incremental Formulation)

Conclusions

- Developed an **experimental and analysis methodology** for characterization of uncured highly aligned discontinuous fiber prepreg at room temperature.
- Demonstrated normalized stress-strain curves **collapse onto a master curve**.
- Formulated a **strain-rate-dependent anisotropic model** capturing:
 - Pre-yield non-linear hardening,
 - Post-yield exponential softening, and
 - Exponential stress decay during relaxation.
- **Validated** model predictions against experimental results.
- Generated a **family of rate-dependent input curves** for forming simulations.
- Formulated Constitutive model in **incremental form** for software implementation.
- Implemented the constitutive model in CAM/CAD software (**AniForm / Abaqus**).
- **Simulated complex** part geometries using Axiom TuFF model.

- Expand mechanical characterization to additional in-plane loading conditions
 - i. Transverse direction (90° to fiber alignment),
 - ii. In-plane shear,
 - iii. Off-axis loading scenarios,that enables a more complete anisotropic material model.
- Investigate thickness deformation (thinning response).
- Characterize temperature-dependent behavior at elevated temperatures.
 - Supports non-isothermal forming simulations.

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